

ANALYSIS OF PSYCHOLOGICAL FACTORS OF THE SPREAD OF CYBERBULLYING EVENTS AMONG UZBEKISTAN YOUNG PEOPLE

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ABSTRACT This article highlights some of the results of scientific research conducted in order to improve the system for protecting the information and psychological safety of the youth of Uzbekistan from the threat of cyberbullying. According to the researcher's hypothesis, as a result of studying the protective mechanisms associated with the endopsychism of the individual in defense against cyberbullying, the psychological factors of the spread of cases of cyberbullying in society have been illuminated (anonymity and the possibility of cyberbullying at any time; problems in the cognitive sphere of the individual's psyche; specific emotional-volitional and need-motivational spheres of the individual's psyche; the presence of negative attitudes that reduce a person's communicative tolerance).

Keywords: psychological factors, cyberbullying, cognitive sphere of the individual's psyche; specific emotional-volitional and need-motivational spheres of the individual's psyche.

АННОТАЦИЯ В статье приведен ряд результатов научного исследования, проведенных в целях совершенствования системы защиты информационной и психологической безопасности молодежи Узбекистана от угрозы кибербуллинга. По гипотезе исследователя, в результате изучения защитных механизмов, связанных с эндопсихикой личности в защите от кибербуллинга, освещены психологические факторы распространения случаев кибербуллинга в обществе. (анонимность и возможность кибербуллинга в любое время; проблемы в когнитивная сфера психики личности; специфические эмоционально-волевая и потребностно-

мотивационная сферы психики личности; наличие негативных установок, снижающих коммуникативную толерантность у человека).

Ключевые слова: психологические факторы, кибербуллинг, когнитивная сфера психики личности; специфические эмоционально-волевую и потребностно-мотивационную сферы психики личности;

INTRODUCTION

In order to study the competencies of protecting youth in Uzbekistan from cyberbullying, we decided to select adolescents¹ (aged 16-19) as the object of our experimental research. This decision was based on content analysis of Uzbek-language video materials available on the Internet, which showed that teenagers are more often involved in and victimized by socially dangerous forms of cyberbullying such as fraping, sexting, cyberstalking, and happy slapping. To identify the psychological mechanisms of protection against forms of cyberbullying among adolescents and to create correctional training programs, we considered it appropriate to carry out empirical work among first-year university students.

Our theoretical study of the cyberbullying threat to the information-psychological security of youth, along with our scientific hypotheses and practical experiments, identified various psychological factors contributing to the spread of cyberbullying incidents. These factors include:

1. The presence of anonymity and the possibility of committing cyberbullying at any time.
2. Problems in the cognitive domain of the individual's psyche.
3. Specific problems in the emotional-volitional and need-motivational domains of the individual's psyche.
4. Specific problems in the domain of behavior management in the individual's psyche.

¹ G'oziyev, E. G. (2010). Ontogenesis Psychology. Tashkent: "Noshir" Publishing House. pp. 214, 216.

5. The presence of low communicative tolerance and negative communicative attitudes.

DISCUSSIONS

Each factor was thoroughly studied, including its causes and the influence of the social environment. For instance:

1. The presence of anonymity and the possibility of committing cyberbullying at any time. Nowadays, almost everyone has access to the Internet. Even young children widely use various gadgets and mobile communication devices, and any person can disseminate information on the Internet, communicate freely on social networks without using their real name. The possibilities and opportunities are virtually limitless. The anonymity preserved on the Internet allows a person to commit cyberbullying at any time. A victim of cyberbullying may suffer 24 hours a day, seven days a week, and may not feel safe even in their own home. With just a few clicks, hundreds or even thousands of people can witness online humiliation. The variety of methods and technologies for committing cyberbullying, unlike traditional bullying, does not require face-to-face contact or physical strength, making it convenient for the initiator and contributing to its widespread occurrence among both youth and adults.

In addition, in the process of upbringing, parents often try to suppress their children's aggression and set restrictions. This can lead to issues with suppressed emotions, such as emotional closure and inability to express feelings in an ecologically acceptable manner. As a result, adolescents may choose anonymous forms of aggression and express their negative opposition position verbally.

2. Problems in the cognitive domain of the individual's psyche. The lack of competence in using the Internet among youth, as well as the failure to recognize that mocking someone online and sharing personal information without consent constitute a violation of widely accepted personal rights², lead to the execution of

² <https://daryo.uz/k/2023/07/19/xonanda-kanizani-instagramda-haqorat-qilgan-talaba-yigit-66-mln-som-jarimaga-tortildi>

cyberbullying acts. There are many such examples. Perpetrators often admit their ignorance of the legal assessment of such situations, and indeed, there is insufficient propaganda about this in school textbooks and social networks. The inability to fully understand the victim's situation, recognize that the consequences of insults can be tragic, and even lead to the victim's death, whether knowingly or intentionally, pertains to cyberbullying initiators. The lack of adequate propaganda and awareness of legal liability criteria is one of the reasons for the widespread occurrence of cyberbullying.

Currently, as part of psychoprophylactic measures, it is advisable to provide young people and parents with guidelines on Internet usage, rules for communicating on social networks, strategies for preventing cyberbullying, and information about cyberbullying through booklets, wall newspapers, pictures, handouts, short films, and placing clear and concise reminders in educational institutions.

It is crucial to adhere to the laws of influence on consciousness and provide the correct instructions to the individual's mind (see Figure 1):

Figure 1. Recommendations for protecting youth from cyberbullying. For parents to protect their children from cyberbullying threats, it is advisable to place clear and concise instructions in the form of advertisements in mass media or reminders in the yards of educational institutions (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. For parents. Protect your child from cyberbullying threats.

CONCLUSION

Specific problems in the emotional-volitional and need-motivational domains of the individual's psyche. Adolescents' inability to fully understand their own and others' emotions can lead to the execution and spread of cyberbullying. The mathematical statistical analysis of the experimental work conducted within the framework of the dissertation and the responses to questionnaire surveys showed that young people often do not fully comprehend their motives for using the Internet. They may use the Internet simply to pass the time, which can lead to mocking others, spreading video materials, and deriving pleasure from it.

References:

1. Patchin, J. W., & Hinduja, S. (2012). Cyberbullying: An Update and Synthesis of the Research. In R. W. Patchin & S. Hinduja (Eds.), *Cyberbullying Prevention and Response: Expert Perspectives* (pp. 13-35). Routledge.
2. Kowalski, R. M., Limber, S. P., & Agatston, P. W. (2012). *Cyberbullying: Bullying in the Digital Age*. Wiley-Blackwell.
3. Smith, P. K., Mahdavi, J., Carvalho, M., Fisher, S., Russell, S., & Tippett, N. (2008). Cyberbullying: Its Nature and Impact in Secondary School Pupils. *Journal of Child Psychology and Psychiatry*, 49(4), 376-385.
4. Hinduja, S., & Patchin, J. W. (2010). Bullying, Cyberbullying, and Suicide. *Archives of Suicide Research*, 14(3), 206-221.
5. Willard, N. E. (2007). *Cyberbullying and Cyberthreats: Responding to the Challenge of Online Social Aggression, Threats, and Distress*. Research Press.